

Influence of Herbergs Two Factor Theory on Retail Job Performance

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ABSTRACT

Today retailing plays a crucial role in most economies because of its large scale and importance at local, national and even International levels. No wonder the sector has also undergone significant changes over the past few decades. On the other hand huge money is also being spent in recruiting and training retail staffs that play an indispensable role in the delivery of service to the customers. The successful relationship between the sales force and customers is however preceded by a motivated sales team. This study is an effort to understand the motivational influence on retail job performance using Herzberg's two factor theory.

1. Introduction

Retailing is a crucial element to most economies, mainly because of its large scale and importance at local, national and even international levels. The retailing sector has undergone continuous and significant changes over the past few decades. New facilities ranging from superstores to retail warehouses have widened the retail landscape across the world. In the retail sector, employees have a direct responsibility on the customer relationship, and this relationship is a powerful factor in a company's success. Salespeople deal directly with their customers, thus their attitudes, behaviours and treatments towards their customers will determine whether customers will become loyal toward the retailers. Companies have been spending millions every year in recruiting, training and compensating their sales personnel so that they would be highly encouraged and inspired to perform well, and hence increased levels of profits accrue to the company (Susan, 2003). In a competitive environment, success of an organization depends on effectiveness of the sales force developing and maintaining customer relationships. In many organizations the sales force compensation costs are between 40% and 75% of the marketing budget (Rouziès, 2011). Having a motivated sales force helps control the costs of an organization which otherwise will incur high expenses due to recruitment, training, wastage of time, loss of customers good will and lower output levels.

2. Review of Literature

Several scholars and studies have been conducted on motivational strategies and sales force performance. Motivation is defined as the psychological process that gives behaviour and direction (Kreitner, 2001). Motivation can be also be defined as those psychological processes that cause the arousal, direction and persistence of voluntary action that are goal directed (Reeve, 2014). Studies point that intrinsic motivation is more important than motivation induced by extrinsic strategies. In the case of the retail setting, Winer and Schiff (1980) have conducted a number of studies using Herzberg's dual factor theory. They found that 'achievement' variable was the highest rated motivator. Likewise, 'making more money' received second highest rating in the study, followed by 'chances of promotion' and 'recognition.' In contrast, Lucas (1985)

discovered that 'supervisor employee relationship' was a significant factor of worker satisfaction in a study of US retail store, and two hygiene factors were reported significantly, namely 'company policy,' and 'relationship with peers'.

The mechanistic theories assume that reward is a major motivator towards a good work performance. While mechanistic theories give no recognition to higher order needs like accomplishment and achievement the cognitive theories focus on what arouses or drives behaviour. Maslow's needs hierarchy theory, Herzberg's two factor theory and Vroom's expectancy theory focus on non financial incentives. Studies conducted in the insurance industry on motivational strategies and sales force performance using the Herzberg's theory in the insurance industry in Kenya also called for further studies on the same line in other industries for comparison and generalization of findings. Hence this study uses the two factor theory to understand the motivational influence on retail sales performance.

3. Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study was to analyse the motivational influence on retail sales performance using Herzberg's Two Factor theory.

4. Research Questions

1. To understand the extent of influence of Herzberg's hygiene factors on retail sales job performance.
2. To understand the extent of influence of Herzberg's motivational factors on retail sales job performance.

5. Methodology of the study

The study employs descriptive research design as it portrays accurately the characteristics of an individual, situation or group. Mugenda & Mugenda , 2003 explain that this design reports the way things are and keeps bias low while increasing the reliability of the study. Convenience sampling was used to collect the data from the respondents. About 100 retail sales staff was taken for the study. The primary data was collected using well structured questionnaires with open and close ended questions. Likert 5 point scale was used to measure the respondent's opinion. The sample size used for the study is

10% of the population and this follows the 10% condition in statistics that sample sizes should not be more than 10%.

6. Discussion & Findings

Gender Profile of Respondents: The study sought to determine the gender profile of the respondents included in the

sample and it can be seen from Fig: 1 that 19% were female and 81% were male. This is representative to the ratio of male and female employees at the company and also shows that both genders were included in the sample study.

Education Profile of Respondents: The highest education profile of the respondents can be seen to be PG degree among 13%, UG degree was among 25%, diploma among 17% and High School education among 41%. It is thus understood that majority of the employees doing retail sales job were having

only high school education. This is also representative of the industry statistics. Further this shows that the respondents had relevant knowledge and thus had ease in addressing the questions and provided the correct responses for the study.

Age, Income & Experience Profile of Respondents: The study shows that 81% were between 18- 34 years age group and those employed in retail sales job in other age groups were also present in smaller numbers. Thus sample included all age groups. The income analysis showed that majority of respondents employed in retail sales earned an income of Rs.5000 – Rs. 10,000. The salary earned was only a moderate salary. The experience profile shows 32% were having an

experience of 1-3 years and 28% had less than 1 year experience, 21% had 6+ years and 19 % had between 3 -6 years experience. This shows respondents with varying experience have been included in the study and thus motivational strategies influence on work performance can be perceived by them and thus this study provides reliable and relevant data.

Table 1: Factors Influencing Retail Job Performance

FACTORS INFLUENCING WORK	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Job factors(HF)	100	1	5	4.05	1.017
Supervisory factors(HF)	100	1	5	4.05	0.935
Achievement(MF)	100	1	5	4.02	1.075
Recognition(MF)	100	1	5	3.96	1.062
Responsibility(MF)	100	1	5	4.10	0.963
Advancement(MF)	100	1	5	3.80	1.017
Work condition(MF)	100	1	5	3.96	1.063
Fun@Work(MF)	100	1	5	4.06	1.038
Work performance(WP)	100	1	5	3.9	1.095

(Source: Computed from primary data)

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation statistics calculated for the various hygiene factors (HF) and motivational factors (MF) along with their mean values. Hygiene factor was measured using 2 constructs and Motivational factor was measured using 6 constructs. The scales used to measure the constructs were adapted for the study from previous research work in order to measure the influencers of work performance as identified by the study. Likert scale, with 1-5 ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree was used to measure the various items in each construct. Similarly principle factor analysis was used on the constructs and the statements were

loaded respectively. Thus the reliability of the scale measures was verified.

7. Influencers of work performance using Regression Analysis

The hypothesis proposed for the study is as follows:

Null Hypothesis H0: There is no significant relationship between the dependent (Work Performance) and independent variables (Hygiene Factor & Motivational Factor).

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.721 ^a	.520	.510	.624

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivational Factors, Hygiene Factors

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

R is the correlation, its value is 0.721 and R square is the degree of determination, its value is 0.520. The R square

determines that work performance is determined to an extent of 52% by the hygiene and motivational factors.

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	40.514	2	20.257	52.102	.000 ^a
	Residual	37.324	96	.389		
	Total	77.838	98			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivational Factors, Hygiene Factors

b. Dependent Variable: Work performance

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

Anova table shows that the significant value is less than 0.01 and hence work performance is significantly predicted by the independent variables at 99% confidence level.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.112	.377		.297	.767
	Hygiene Factors	.506	.157	.406	3.222	.002
	Motivational Factors	.438	.159	.348	2.761	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Work performance

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

The regression equation is thus given as follows from the above coefficients table;

Work Performance = 0.112 + 0.506(hygiene factors) + 0.438(Motivational Factors)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.633 ^a	.401	.395	.691
2	.729 ^b	.531	.522	.614
3	.760 ^c	.578	.565	.586
4	.774 ^d	.599	.582	.574

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employees cooperate with other employees at workplace

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employees cooperate with other employees at workplace, I enjoy my work

c. Predictors: (Constant), Employees cooperate with other employees at workplace, I enjoy my work, I have a feeling of personal worth in my job

d. Predictors: (Constant), Employees cooperate with other employees at workplace, I enjoy my work, I have a feeling of personal worth in my job, My organisation has safe work environment

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

As hygiene factors significantly influences work performance as seen from the regression equation above, Stepwise regression model is applied to the various influencers of work performance to clearly identify the most significant influencers of work performance.

SPSS built a model in 4 steps and our final adjusted R square is 0.599, which means that our predictors account for 60% of the variance in overall work performance.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.169	.331		.512	.610	-.487	.826		
4 Employees cooperate with other employees at workplace	.332	.069	.370	4.813	.000	.195	.469	.723	1.383
I enjoy my work	.257	.067	.286	3.847	.000	.124	.390	.770	1.298
I have a feeling of personal worth in my job	.179	.064	.212	2.783	.007	.051	.307	.736	1.359
My organisation has safe work environment	.169	.077	.170	2.197	.030	.016	.322	.714	1.401

a. Dependent Variable: Work performance
(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

In our coefficients table, we only look at our fourth and final model. Like we predicted, our b-coefficients are all significant and in logical directions. Because all predictors have identical (Likert) scales, we prefer interpreting the b-coefficients. Our final model states that

$$\text{Work Performance} = 0.440 + 0.332(\text{JF}) + 0.257(\text{MF}) + 0.179(\text{MF}) + 0.169(\text{MF})$$

Our strongest predictor is Job Factor (Employee cooperation with other employees at workplace): a 1 point increase is associated with a 0.440 point increase in WP (overall work performance). Our model doesn't prove that this relation is causal but it seems reasonable that improving Employee cooperation with other employees at workplace will cause slightly higher overall work performance at work place.

8. Conclusion & Recommendations for future

Employee motivation is directly related to the productivity of an organisation. In the long run it helps to build employee morale and helps to retain talented workforce. This study tries to identify the impact of motivational influence on employee work performance using Herzberg's two factors theory. Here the impact of hygiene factors (Job factors and Supervisory Factors) and Motivational factors (Achievement Advancement, Recognition and Responsibility) were studied and all these factors were found to be rated quite good (4) on a Likert scale of 1 to 5 (80%). This is in tandem with studies that report

satisfaction enhances happiness and productiveness among the workforce (Friend, Johnson, Luthans, & Sohi, 2016; Peterson, Balthazard, Waldman, & Thatcher, 2008)

The study clearly shows that both hygiene and motivational factors available at the company are satisfactory to the employee. This shows a positive company work culture prevailing in the company. But Stepwise Regression analysis has clearly identified that the hygiene factor (job factor) namely "Employee cooperation with other employees at workplace" is the most significant factor influencing work performance at the company. However as Herzberg says that hygiene factors are only maintenance factors whereby their absence will cause dissatisfaction but their presence or increase will not increase the level of work performance. Further the net significant factor influencing work performance is " I enjoy my work" which is a motivational factor and hence the company should plan and organise better activities to keep the work place interesting and avoid the monotony at the work place which is an important component of the retail job

However the company should identify new policies and programs from time to time to sustain this good morale otherwise employees might get bored and become demotivated.

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